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ARTISTIC FEATURES OF THE MONUMENTAL PAINTINGS OF PEOPLE'S ARTIST OKTAY SHIKHALIYEV

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ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ МОНУМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ЖИВОПИСНЫХ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ НАРОДНОГО ХУДОЖНИКА ОКТАЯ ШЫХАЛИЕВА

Abstract.

The article examines the artistic features of the monumental paintings of People's Artist of Azerbaijan Oktay Shikhaliyev, one of the first professional monumental artists in Azerbaijan. Special attention is given to the analysis of his creative activity in the context of the development of Azerbaijani visual art in the 1960s.

It is noted that O. Shikhaliyev actively participated in the artistic decoration of public buildings such as cultural centers, schools, metro stations, restaurants, cafes, and the city circus. In his monumental works he skillfully combined fresco painting, mosaic, ceramics, and other decorative materials. His works are characterized by a decorative style, rich color solutions, carefully constructed compositions, and a harmonious connection with architectural space.

The article analyzes several of the artist's monumental works, including the panel "Peace, Labor, Freedom, Equality, Brotherhood and Happiness" (1961), the decoration of the "Children's World" department store (1963), frescoes in the "Novbahar" restaurant (1964), the mosaic composition in the "Mother and Child" café (1965), and the mosaic panel "Towards the Stars" (1968). Despite the influence of Soviet ideology, the artist incorporated elements of national culture into his compositions, such as traditional ornaments, carpet motifs, and miniature-style details.

The study concludes that the monumental-decorative creativity of Oktay Shikhaliyev occupies an important place in the history of Azerbaijani art. His works became part of the urban artistic environment and played a significant role in shaping public aesthetic taste.

Аннотация.

В статье рассматриваются художественные особенности монументальных живописных произведений народного художника Азербайджана Октая Шыхалиева, одного из первых профессиональных мастеров монументально-декоративного искусства в Азербайджане. Особое внимание уделяется анализу его творческой деятельности в контексте развития азербайджанского изобразительного искусства 1960-х годов.

Отмечается, что О. Шыхалиев активно участвовал в художественном оформлении общественных зданий - домов культуры, школ, станций метро, ресторанов, кафе, цирка и других архитектурных объектов. В его монументальных работах органично сочетаются фресковая живопись, мозаика, керамика и другие декоративные материалы. Его произведения характеризуются декоративностью, насыщенным колоритом, продуманной композицией и гармоничным взаимодействием с архитектурной средой.

В статье анализируются такие произведения художника, как панно «Мир, Труд, Свобода, Равенство, Братство и Счастье» (1961), оформление магазина «Детский мир» (1963), фрески ресторана «Новбахар» (1964), мозаичная композиция кафе «Мать и ребёнок» (1965), а также панно «К звёздам» (1968). Отмечается, что, несмотря на влияние советской идеологии, художник стремился включать в свои композиции элементы национальной культуры - орнаменты, мотивы коврового искусства и миниатюрной живописи.

В результате исследования делается вывод о том, что монументально-декоративное творчество Октая Шыхалиева занимает важное место в истории азербайджанского искусства. Его произведения стали частью художественной среды города и сыграли значительную роль в формировании эстетического вкуса общества.

Keywords: Oktay Shikhaliyev, monumental painting, monumental-decorative art, Azerbaijani visual art, mosaic, fresco, Soviet period art, synthesis of architecture and art, decorative composition.

Ключевые слова: Октай Шыхалиев, монументальная живопись, монументально-декоративное искусство, азербайджанское изобразительное искусство, мозаика, фреска, искусство советского периода, синтез архитектуры и искусства, декоративная композиция.

The 1960s are remembered in Azerbaijani visual art as a period marked by the emergence of a new generation of artists. During this time, People's Artist Oktay Shikhaliyev held a special place among the painters who worked consistently in both easel and monumental painting. His signature can be seen in the artistic decoration of many public buildings across the republic, including cultural centers, schools, metro stations, restaurants, cafés, the city circus, and other architectural spaces. As the head of the decorative and applied arts section of the Artists' Union, he put forward important initiatives for the development of Azerbaijani monumental-decorative art and played a significant role in attracting young artists to this field.

Oktay Shikhaliyev, one of the first professional monumental artists of Azerbaijan, was born in September 1931 in the city of Baku. The ancient everyday traditions of the Absheron Peninsula, old residential houses, attractive nature, bright sun, the ever-changing views of the Caspian Sea, and the landscapes shaped by the winds played an important role in forming his worldview and influencing his future professional choice.

After graduating from the Art School with honors in 1952, Oktay Shikhaliyev's dedication to art took him to Saint Petersburg (formerly Leningrad). In the same year, he entered the V. Mukhina Higher School of Art and Industry, where he received systematic training in monumental-decorative art, applied art forms, ceramics, and mosaic techniques. By working in the studios of well-known Russian artists, he enriched both his artistic-technical skills and theoretical knowledge. After successfully graduating from the institution in 1958, O. Shikhaliyev returned to his native Baku and soon began actively participating in the artistic decoration of public buildings in different regions of the republic. Even during his student years, he successfully participated in various exhibitions and attracted attention in 1957 when he was awarded the first prize in decorative art at the All-Union Youth Exhibition Festival.

In his monumental works, Oktay Shikhaliyev skillfully used not only fresco painting but also mosaic, tiles, and other decorative materials. Although the main direction of his creativity was connected with monumental-decorative art, the artist also worked in different genres of visual art. His diverse activity included portrait and landscape compositions in easel painting, poster design, decoration of vases and plates, small thematic panels, as well as experiments in ceramics and metal casting. Nevertheless, monumental painting and decorative compositions remained the main focus of his creativity. His painting style is distinctly decorative and is based on the emotional expressive possibilities of color.

One of the first important examples of the artist's monumental creativity is the panel titled "Peace, Labor, Freedom, Equality, Brotherhood and Happiness," created in 1961 for the boarding school in the city of Ganja. As the title suggests, the ideological content of the work is based on the promotion of ideas of peace, friendship, and brotherhood. In the context of Soviet ideology, the glorification of unity, friendship, and

brotherhood among all peoples, as well as the depiction of workers struggling for peace, was one of the main directions in the creativity of artists.

In this work, O. Shikhaliyev created a large composition that combines the idea of peace with the motifs of labor, freedom, equality, and brotherhood. The panel skillfully unites images of people from different professions, workers, symbols of peace, and scenes that express the idea of a happy future. This monumental work was created in collaboration with another monumental artist, A. Agamalov. One of the main advantages of the work is the artistic expression of actual social ideas on a large architectural surface of the school's façade.

In 1963, the artist, together with Huseyn Rajabov, carried out the artistic decoration of the "Kid world" department store in Baku. The three large interior walls of the store were decorated with paintings depicting various scenes from the everyday life of children. The general idea of the compositions was devoted to the theme of peace, in accordance with the slogan "Let the Sun Always Shine."

The authors presented the idea of peace through the eyes of children, using a "childlike language," portraying children as the carriers of sunlight, brightness, joy, and hope as the future generation. In this composition, children are presented as the guardians of peace and the owners of tomorrow, while the image of the sun symbolizes both the continuity of life and positive energy and optimism. This monumental composition stood out for its high artistic quality in accordance with the artistic requirements of its time and for many years was remembered as a successful example of monumental decorative design.

One characteristic feature of Oktay Shikhaliyev's monumental panels is that, alongside themes reflecting Soviet ideology, the works also include motifs referring to the distant past and national roots. In monumental artworks of the Soviet period, the prominent presence of Lenin's image and symbols representing communist ideology was largely determined by political requirements. However, despite these limitations, O. Shikhaliyev attempted to bring a national spirit into his compositions by incorporating national ornaments, carpet motifs, and details inspired by miniature painting.

Among the monumental decorative works created by the artist together with Huseyn Rajabov, special mention can be made of the lyrical frescoes on the walls of the "Novbahar" restaurant in Baku in 1964, the mosaic composition created in the "Mother and Child" café in 1965, and the monumental scenes decorating the foyer of the Baku Circus in 1968. In these compositions, scenes of everyday life, motifs of celebration and leisure, as well as elements related to sports and circus art are presented both in decorative and narrative forms. The sensitivity in the use of color and form, as well as the precise application of compositional principles, demonstrates that the artists had a deep understanding of the technical and artistic subtleties of monumental-decorative art.

The 1960s can be considered the most intensive period of Oktay Shikhaliyev's activity as a monumental artist. During these years, he constantly searched for

new solutions in terms of form, material, and ideological content. He was inclined toward experimentation and did not hesitate to start again when he was not satisfied with the result.

One of the successful results of these creative searches is the mosaic panel titled "Towards the Stars," created in 1968 on the facade of the new building of School No. 18 in Baku. In this composition, which reflects cosmic space, the figures of a young boy and girl holding a space device in their extended hands are depicted as if ready to fly toward the sun, the stars, and the infinite universe. The central idea of the composition is the concept that knowledge and science lead humanity "toward the stars." In this work, the artist connects the romantic image of cosmic space with the importance of education and science, creating a logical connection between the functional purpose of the school building and the ideological theme of the panel. The dynamic plasticity of both figures, the constructive use of color, and the volumetric solution that harmonizes with the surrounding environment clearly reveal O. Shikhaliyev's professional monumental thinking. Unfortunately, some of these works have been dismantled over time for various reasons, and like many monumental artworks that once decorated the urban environment, they have been lost.

Another successful work by O. Shikhaliyev is the monumental panel created in 1969 for the interior of the Bilajari locomotive depot station in the Azerbaijani railway system. In this complex multi-figure composition, the free and joyful labor of Soviet people is glorified. The flag of the Soviet state, the portrait of Lenin, images of labor heroes, and scenes reflecting the rhythm of production are united within a single compositional system. The main idea of the work is the celebration of happy and creative labor, as well as economic and social achievements. The composition is perfectly connected with the interior architecture of the building, and the clarity of the plot line and the completeness of the images form the main artistic qualities of the work.

Oktay Shikhaliyev can truly be described as a hardworking and dedicated artist. He was constantly active, participating in republican and all-Union exhibitions, attending meetings of various artistic councils, and traveling to different regions and foreign countries for creative missions. The high demands placed on the artistic design of public and industrial buildings in that period required artists to take great responsibility in

everything from the selection of ideological themes to compositional solutions. The synthesis of monumental-decorative art with architecture was intended to create an artistic environment reflecting different aspects of the life of Soviet society.

In this context, architecture faced important challenges, ranging from the design of large ensembles to the artistic solutions of individual public buildings. Masters of monumental-decorative art had to skillfully use colored majolica, tiles, stained glass, wall ornaments, shabaka patterns, metal decorative elements, sculptural reliefs, large-scale decorative ceramic works, and other visual means. The synthesis of art and architecture created an "artistic environment" that influenced people both visually and ideologically, contributing to the formation of public aesthetic taste and enriching the spiritual world of individuals.

Conclusion. As a result, the monumental-decorative creativity of Oktay Shikhaliyev formed one of the leading directions in the history of Azerbaijani monumental art. Based on folk creativity, the rich heritage of national architecture, wall paintings, ornaments carved on wood and stone, carpet weaving, and examples of applied art, this artistic line gradually developed into a highly professional stage and made it possible to create works of art with strong spiritual and aesthetic impact.

The monumental works created as a result of the artist's artistic thinking have become part of public memory and have played a role in shaping the ideological and aesthetic taste of society. Many works bearing the signature of Oktay Shikhaliyev, located in hotel complexes, factories, streets and squares, as well as on the façades and interiors of schools and medical institutions in the city of Baku, have been dismantled over time for various reasons. Nevertheless, from an artistic point of view, they continue to preserve their significance and relevance.

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